

**THE DETERMINATION OF IMPACT OF LITERARY TEXTS
THROUGH ANALYTICAL HIERARCHICAL PROCESS ON
DEVELOPMENT OF FUNDAMENTAL LANGUAGE SKILLS IN
TEACHING OF TURKISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE**

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Abstract:

The objective of this study is to identify the influence of literary texts on development of basic language skills in Turkish language teaching as a foreign language by using Analytical Hierarchical Process. Degree of importance of instrumentalism varies depending on the genres and factors such as the level of language that is being taught and the age group of learners. Primary witnesses in identifying the functionality level of literary texts upon the competence of language carriers in teaching Turkish as a foreign language are undoubtedly the teachers of Turkish. Provided always expert opinions are received and relevant sources are reviewed, the criteria, sub criteria and alternatives required for literary texts to be used for teaching of Turkish language as a foreign language, and data have been collected in face-to-face meetings with experts that teach Turkish as a foreign language. Analytical Hierarchical System has been used for analysing the data collected. According to the findings obtained, it has been determined that cultural transmission and vocabulary both play an important role for improved language skills in teaching Turkish as a foreign language. It has however been further observed that there were very few literary texts prepared according to language levels intended for use as a source in teaching Turkish as a foreign language to foreign speakers.

Keywords: teaching of Turkish language, foreign language, literary texts, AHP

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1. Introduction

Humans, as social beings, need to communicate in order to continue living in a social environment. This is possible through language and socialization. Communities, too, use the language when contacting with the representatives of other communities. Although language is a medium that establishes contact between individuals and societies, it carries its social function through literature. Relationships between language and communication as well as socialization and literature are two inseparable components.

Language, defined as a system of double-jointed audible indicators specific to a particular group of people, and a social product of language skills according to a definition made by Saussure and recognized by many linguists, is a conventional layout that enables individuals to use this skill and is adopted by the society. It is a mechanism that is formed both by mixture of those that show and are shown, and includes indicators which are the products of this mixture and operational rules of the components that were created by them. According to Martinet's famous definition: *"Language is an information tool that allows human experience to be separated into units, in other words, into morphemes that include a vocal expression with semantic content in forms ranging from community to community; this vocal expression is articulated in the form of distinct and successive units, in other words, phonemes, that are found in each language at certain number and whose attributes and mutual relations range from one language to another"* (Vardar, 2002:71). Saussure and Martinet, with these definitions, pointed out the aspects of language being a medium of communication and a social institution that connects communities together. The social aspect of language is related to the culture of that society. Literature is an important carrier of the culture. Therefore, it is possible to teach these two aspects in order foreign language teaching to reach its objective.

Approaching the issue of language from a different perspective, Kaplan (2001) states that fact that language is the liveliest part of human beings and of life, there is a very thin and knitted vessel and neural relationship between words and the life and, in this context, this is what that makes language, consisting of small voice organisms, as important as the life itself. Kaplan also emphasizes the sound and connection of language, but this connection is directly related to literature.

Aksan (2009) defined the language in the institutional context as such: *"Language is a magical being that is versatile beyond the grasp of our understanding at once, indicates different attributes when looking at it from various angles, and whose some mysteries we failed to solve even today. Language is a multifaceted asset intertwined with social life which is related*

with all areas that cannot be considered separately either with human beings, societies or human beings and societies such as science, art, technique, etc., and, at the same time, seen as an institution that constitutes them." The aspect of language as a living being is an element that keeps it alive. Literary texts are the best ways of transporting it to the future together with this element. It is possible, by literary texts, to carry the language to advanced stages and take it to a certain level in foreign language teaching.

Although it is concrete in words and phrases, language is the leading element for the spiritual life of the nation as a medium in the formation of its meaning, purpose, feeling and imagination. It can also be defined as a meaning that was molded and settled within centuries and in the minds of generations (Başgil, 2010).

Rousseau (2009) stated that *"...the first histories, addresses and laws were written in verse, poetry was discovered before the invention of writing and how strong was the domain of poetry from then and until now. In this context, he expressed that the perception of speaking and singing in first times was the same thing by his expression that "at first, there was no music other than melody and no melody other than the changing sound of words."*

No language remained as it was first spoken and they survived until today after going through various stages. Levend (1973) states that language is a living being that serves the society, changed due to new necessities that appeared in time and community, observed the way of living, conception, world-view and pleasures of the period parallel to the relationship between life and literature, changes could be in words, phrases and sentence structure and it is also typical that these changes can be contrary to the rules of the grammar.

According to Saussure (1998), it is a bad practice to describe phenomenon through words and Saussure sums up the attributes of language thus; *"Language owes its existence only to a kind of contract between the members of the community. On the other hand, individuals need to learn the language in order to know its function. Even a person, who suffers from aphasia, does not lose the language if he/she understands the audible indicators that he/she hears. Language is something that is so distinct. We do not speak dead languages now, but we can learn their linguistic order. It is an arrangement of indicators. The important thing in this arrangement is the significant combination of hearing images and two sides of this indicator are intellectual at the same rate"*.

Chomsky (2011) states that knowing a language does not only mean knowing the grammatical rules of that language and notes having the command of a language as such: *"In principle, it means being able to understand what was said and being in a position to be able to produce a signal by an intended interpretation of meaning. We cannot interpret the thing uttered before us only by looking at linguistic principles that determine the vocal and*

inference properties of the utterance. The extra-linguistic beliefs about speaker and situation also play a fundamental role in determining the ways of production, discernment and understanding." Language acquisition also indicates that language is governed by the principles of cognitive structure without appearances as well as the presence of extra-linguistic elements of the mentioned language. The best way of learning extra-linguistic elements can be through literary texts.

Aktaş and Gündüz (2004), speaking of the definition of language and the role of language skills in the acquisition in foreign language teaching, state that the most important factor enabling the communication between people is, no doubt, the magical being that we call language. This being necessitates the learning "speaking-listening" skills and skills of "comprehending" what was listened for verbal communication and "writing – reading" skills and skills of "comprehending" what was read for written communications. How acquiring these skills is prerequisite in learning our own native language, it is also a prerequisite in learning any foreign language. In this context, instrumentality of literary texts is of the utmost importance in the acquisition of these skills.

2. Methodology

2.1. Research method

In addition to using descriptive statistics as a method, Analytic Hierarchy Process, one of the multi-criteria decision-making techniques that can evaluate both objective and subjective data, was used in the research. It is unlikely to evaluate subjective criteria with other statistical methods. AHP was preferred as a method since subjective data can be evaluated more accurately with it.

AHP is an important tool because it uses both objective and subjective evaluation criteria, provides testing for the consistency of evaluations, and especially allows decision-maker to implement a very important decision like which one of the alternatives among many, which needed to be evaluated in accordance with a large number of criteria, should be given priority in the process (Eraslan and Algun, 2005:98). AHP is a method that helps to cope with risk and uncertainty, intuitions, logical and illogical decisions in complex situations. The most obvious advantage of this method is that it includes subjective factors in decision-making process. AHP is based on the principle of taking knowledge and experiences that are as valuable as data into account in case of decision-making (Hacikoylu, 2006:16).

2.2. Population and sample

Teachers, who work in government institutions and private companies and teach Turkish as a foreign language, constitute the population of the research. The sampling group of the research is teachers who teach Turkish as a foreign language in Georgia, Turkey, Russia, Pakistan, South Africa, Mozambique, Colombia, Romania, Kosovo, Egypt, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Ukraine, Albania, Nigeria, Turkmenistan, Sweden, Kazakhstan, Iraq, Australia, United States, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Cameroon, Azerbaijan, Mongolia and Afghanistan. The purposeful sampling, one of the improbable sampling methods, was used as a sampling method.

2.3. Data collection and analysis

In the research, resources, such as books, theses, articles, proceedings, internet sites, etc., on language teaching, foreign language teaching, teaching Turkish as a foreign language and using literary texts in language teaching were scanned. Data collection tool was developed in accordance with the information gathered. The survey, which was prepared after obtaining expert opinions and whose validity tested, was used to collect the data. In addition to collecting data through mail or internet as data collection method, data were collected from teachers via one-to-one or telephone conversation.

Microsoft Office Excel and SPSS programs were used in the analysis of data. The collected data were transferred to the computer environment after being organized, analysis results were reached by performing necessary formulation processes and the findings were interpreted.

3. Findings and comments

The survey, which was prepared for the purpose of collecting data in the research, was administered to 71 students. Some of the teachers, who participated in the research, have taught Turkish in more than one country in the world. The participants are seen to be made up of teachers who teach Turkish to students from a total of 26 countries, such as Georgia, Turkey, Russia, Pakistan, South Africa, Mozambique, Colombia, Romania, Kosovo, Egypt, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Ukraine, Albania, Nigeria, Turkmenistan, Sweden, Kazakhstan, Iraq, Australia, United States, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Cameroon, Azerbaijan, Mongolia and Afghanistan. It is an important phenomenon in terms of objectivity of the research that participants worked in countries with different language structures and culture, studied their mother languages in conveyed countries, and taught Turkish not in the country where it is spoken but in the setting of the countries where they remain. The sample group was not only chosen from teachers who teach

Turkish at a certain level, but was chosen from those teach Turkish as a foreign language at all levels. The participation of teachers working in different countries is important in teaching literary texts not only from a few countries but from different geographies.

While teachers in 20-30 age range were seen to constitute 52.1%, those in 31-40 age range 35.2% and those in 41-50 age range 12.7% when considering the age range of the participants to the research. Half of the participants being young and half of them being in the middle age range indicate that the research did not only focus on certain age group. The participation of subjects with different age and life experience is important for the reliability of the research. In this context, young participants' creation of a dynamic structure and their openness to innovation are one of the strong points of the research.

83.1% of participating teachers consisted of males and 16.9% of them were females. The selection of participants from both males and females is quite important for the collection of all desired perspectives. Certain literary genres should be considered to have naturally more impact on the masculine and feminine genders.

Professional experience of Turkish language teachers, who participated in the research, is an important factor in terms of achieving the correct data. According to the data, the ratio of teachers with 1-5 years of experience is 45.1%, that of teachers with 6-15 years of experience is 36.6% and the rate of teachers with more than 15 years of experience is 16.8%. 55% of participants, having over 6 years of experience, are one of the most powerful aspects of the research.

In the research, the geometric means of the obtained data were taken by transferring them into Microsoft Excel environment, their paired comparison matrixes were determined, their weights were calculate and consistency tests were conducted. 9 comparison matrixes were created in the research, the consistency ratios of each of them were calculated and the accuracy of averages for the obtained responses was tested. These processes are determined below step by step.

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Table 3.1: Paired Comparison Matrix for Main Criteria

Language Skills	Speaking	Listening Comprehension	Reading	Writing	Teaching Vocabulary	Teaching Grammar	Culture Transfer
Speaking	1.00	2.45	2.61	2.62	1.95	3.86	2.74
Listening Comprehension	0.41	1.00	1.95	2.16	2.14	2.97	3.39
Reading	0.38	0.51	1.00	2.48	1.66	2.94	2.83
Writing	0.38	0.46	0.40	1.00	1.85	2.40	3.04
Teaching Vocabulary	0.51	0.47	0.60	0.54	1.00	2.66	2.77
Teaching Grammar	0.26	0.34	0.34	0.42	0.38	1.00	2.70
Culture Transfer	0.37	0.29	0.35	0.33	0.36	0.37	1.00
Toplam	3.31	5.52	7.26	9.56	9.35	16.20	18.47

In Table 3.1., each column was added separately in order to calculate the significance level of each criterion.

Table 3.2: Matrix Calculation of Main Criteria

Language Skills	Speaking	Listening Comprehension	Reading	Writing	Teaching Vocabulary	Teaching Grammar	Culture Transfer
Speaking	$\frac{1}{3.31}$	$\frac{2.45}{5.52}$	$\frac{2.61}{7.26}$	$\frac{2.62}{9.56}$	$\frac{1.95}{9.35}$	$\frac{3.86}{16.20}$	$\frac{2.74}{18.47}$
Listening Comprehension	$\frac{0.41}{3.31}$	$\frac{1}{5.52}$	$\frac{1.95}{7.26}$	$\frac{2.16}{9.56}$	$\frac{2.14}{9.35}$	$\frac{2.97}{16.20}$	$\frac{3.39}{18.47}$
Reading	$\frac{0.38}{3.31}$	$\frac{0.51}{5.52}$	$\frac{1}{7.26}$	$\frac{2.48}{9.56}$	$\frac{1.66}{9.35}$	$\frac{2.94}{16.20}$	$\frac{2.83}{18.47}$
Writing	$\frac{0.38}{3.31}$	$\frac{0.46}{5.52}$	$\frac{0.40}{7.26}$	$\frac{1}{9.56}$	$\frac{1.85}{9.35}$	$\frac{2.40}{16.20}$	$\frac{3.04}{18.47}$
Teaching Vocabulary	$\frac{0.51}{3.31}$	$\frac{0.47}{5.52}$	$\frac{0.60}{7.26}$	$\frac{0.54}{9.56}$	$\frac{1}{9.35}$	$\frac{2.66}{16.20}$	$\frac{2.77}{18.47}$
Teaching Grammar	$\frac{0.26}{3.31}$	$\frac{0.34}{5.52}$	$\frac{0.34}{7.26}$	$\frac{0.42}{9.56}$	$\frac{0.38}{9.35}$	$\frac{1}{16.20}$	$\frac{2.70}{18.47}$
Culture Transfer	$\frac{0.37}{3.31}$	$\frac{0.29}{5.52}$	$\frac{0.35}{7.26}$	$\frac{0.33}{9.56}$	$\frac{0.36}{9.35}$	$\frac{0.37}{16.20}$	$\frac{1}{18.47}$

In Figure 3.2., each element in this matrix was divided into the discovered total value. Matrix, obtained as a result of division, was formed like in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3: Significance Levels of Main Criteria

Language Skills	Speaking	Listening Comprehension	Reading	Writing	Teaching Vocabulary	Teaching Grammar	Culture Transfer	Significance Level
Speaking	0.30	0.44	0.36	0.27	0.21	0.24	0.15	0.28
Listening Comprehension	0.12	0.18	0.27	0.23	0.23	0.18	0.18	0.20
Reading	0.12	0.09	0.14	0.26	0.18	0.18	0.15	0.16
Writing	0.12	0.08	0.06	0.10	0.20	0.15	0.16	0.12
Teaching Vocabulary	0.15	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.11	0.16	0.15	0.11
Teaching Grammar	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.15	0.07
Culture Transfer	0.11	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.05	0.05

The averages of matrixes, formed as a result of the division, were taken in Figure 4.1.7 and the significance level of each criterion was found. According to the findings, it was concluded that literary texts, used in teaching Turkish as a foreign language, were used effectively on speaking skills with an effect of 28%. This was followed by listening-comprehension with 20%, by reading with 16%, by writing with 12%, by teaching vocabulary with 11%, by teaching grammar with 7% and by culture transfer with 5% respectively. It was discovered by this situation that literary texts were not included sufficiently in teaching Turkish to foreigner either in textbooks or reading books within the context of culture transfer. In addition this, they were not also used in teaching grammar and vocabulary. It can be said that literary texts for speaking, listening comprehension and reading are adequately used in teaching Turkish to foreigners.

In the next stage, consistency tests are conducted. Consistency test is needed to measure the reliability of the significance levels in literary texts used in the development of language skills. Phases and calculations, applied in consistency test, were indicated below step by step. The first phase of consistency test is the multiplication of paired comparison matrix with significance levels matrix. The following figures were reached as a result of multiplication.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1.00 & 2.45 & 2.61 & 2.62 & 1.95 & 3.86 & 2.74 \\ 0.41 & 1.00 & 1.95 & 2.16 & 2.14 & 2.97 & 3.39 \\ 0.38 & 0.51 & 1.00 & 2.48 & 1.66 & 2.94 & 2.83 \\ 0.38 & 0.46 & 0.40 & 1.00 & 1.85 & 2.40 & 3.04 \\ 0.51 & 0.47 & 0.60 & 0.54 & 1.00 & 2.66 & 2.77 \\ 0.26 & 0.34 & 0.34 & 0.42 & 0.38 & 1.00 & 2.70 \\ 0.37 & 0.29 & 0.35 & 0.33 & 0.36 & 0.37 & 1.00 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0.28 \\ 0.20 \\ 0.16 \\ 0.12 \\ 0.11 \\ 0.07 \\ 0.05 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \times 0.28 + 2.45 \times 0.20 + 2.61 \times 0.16 + 2.62 \times 0.12 + 1.95 \times 0.11 + 3.86 \times 0.07 + 2.74 \times 0.05 \\ 0.41 \times 0.28 + 1 \times 0.20 + 1.95 \times 0.16 + 2.16 \times 0.12 + 2.14 \times 0.11 + 2.97 \times 0.07 + 3.39 \times 0.05 \\ 0.38 \times 0.28 + 0.51 \times 0.20 + 1 \times 0.16 + 2.48 \times 0.12 + 1.66 \times 0.11 + 2.94 \times 0.07 + 2.83 \times 0.05 \\ 0.38 \times 0.28 + 0.46 \times 0.20 + 0.40 \times 0.16 + 1 \times 0.12 + 1.85 \times 0.11 + 2.40 \times 0.07 + 3.04 \times 0.05 \\ 0.51 \times 0.28 + 0.47 \times 0.20 + 0.60 \times 0.16 + 0.54 \times 0.12 + 1 \times 0.11 + 2.66 \times 0.07 + 2.77 \times 0.05 \\ 0.26 \times 0.28 + 0.34 \times 0.20 + 0.34 \times 0.16 + 0.42 \times 0.12 + 0.38 \times 0.11 + 1 \times 0.07 + 2.70 \times 0.05 \\ 0.37 \times 0.28 + 0.29 \times 0.20 + 0.35 \times 0.16 + 0.33 \times 0.12 + 0.36 \times 0.11 + 0.37 \times 0.07 + 1 \times 0.05 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 2.14 \\ 1.52 \\ 1.22 \\ 0.92 \\ 0.84 \\ 0.50 \\ 0.38 \end{pmatrix}$$

In the second phase, each element of this matrix was divided by significance levels and their averages were taken.

$$\frac{2.14}{0.28} = 7.59, \frac{1.52}{0.20} = 7.61, \frac{1.22}{0.16} = 7.61, \frac{0.92}{0.12} = 7.41, \frac{0.84}{0.11} = 7.35, \frac{0.50}{0.07} = 7.29, \frac{0.38}{0.05} = 7.29$$

$$\frac{7.59 + 7.61 + 7.61 + 7.41 + 7.35 + 7.29 + 7.29}{7} = 7.45$$

The values resulting from calculations were placed in $\frac{\lambda_{\max} - n}{n - 1}$ average formula and a new result was reached. This is the size of $\lambda_{\max}$ n matrix.

$$\frac{7.45 - 7}{7 - 1} = \frac{0.45}{6} = 0.075$$

This value is divided by previously determined consistency index and consistency ratio was identified. Consistency index value for a matrix of 7x7 in size is 1.35.

$$\frac{0.075}{1.35} = 0.056$$

The conducted process is understood to be consistent since the value of the calculated consistency ratio 0.056 (5.56 %) is smaller than the value of 0, 10 (10%).

3.1. Paired comparison rates and significance levels of literary texts effectively used in the acquisition of language skills

Stories were found to be the most effective literary texts with 13% when considering the significance levels of the literary texts in the acquisition of language skills. Fairy tales ranked in the second with 10%. The ranking, according to significance levels, was measured as poetry, novels and fables with 9%, memoirs, conversation-interviews with 7%, dairies with 6%, biographies, commentaries and heater plays with 5%, essays and letters with 4%, anecdotes, proverbs-idioms with 3%, and tongue twisters with 2%.

Table 3.4: Significance Levels and Consistency Ratios of Sub-criteria in terms of Literary Texts
 in the Acquisition of Language Skills

	Significance Level	Consistency
Poetry	0.09	
Stories	0.13	
Novel	0.09	
Fable	0.09	
Fairy Tales	0.10	
Memoirs	0.07	
Conversation-Interview	0.07	
Dairies	0.06	
Biographies	0.05	7.60%
Commentary	0.05	
Essay	0.04	
Theater plays	0.05	
Letters	0.04	
Anecdotes	0.03	
Proverbs-Idioms	0.03	
Tongue twisters	0.02	

According to the findings, it can be concluded that teachers use stories the more from literary texts in teaching Turkish in FLT and this was followed by fairy tales, poetry, novels and fables. The reason why proverbs, idioms and tongue twisters achieved lower percentages can be explained because the participants do not see them as literary texts and anecdotes might have been considered in cultural transmission. It is quite normal that letters achieved low ratios considering the fact that they are no longer in use and electronic mail and other messaging programs are used instead. It may be accurate to consider while preparing literary texts in textbooks and reading books in this context.

3.2. Paired comparison ratios and significance levels of sub-criteria in terms of speaking criterion

According to Table 4.3.2, poetry was found to be the most effective literary texts with 17% for the development of speaking skills in teaching Turkish as a FL. Stories and fairy tales ranked in the second significance level with 15%. While fables ranked in the third significance level, memoirs, conversation-interview were used by 8%, commentaries and theater plays by 7%, anecdotes by 5%, proverbs-idioms by 4% and tongue twisters by 3% in the development of speaking skills.

Table 3.5: Significant Levels and Consistency Ratios of Sub-criteria in terms of
 Speaking Criterion

Speaking	Significance Level	Consistency
Poetry	0.17	
Stories	0.15	
Fables	0.10	
Fairy Tales	0.15	
Memoirs	0.08	
Conversation-Interviews	0.08	6.31%
Commentary	0.07	
Theater plays	0.07	
Anecdotes	0.05	
Proverbs-Idioms	0.04	
Tongue twisters	0.03	

The selection of appropriate poems for the class level, taking the types of poems and their characteristics into account, helps students to learn the language enjoyably. Being a rich source as a material in foreign language teaching, poetry can contribute to the development of that language when presented with suitable methods, techniques and activities in the teaching process (Ögeyik, 2007:2). The prominence of poetry category in the Turkish Olympiads may be considered a phenomenon that affects this outcome. The findings of this research also support this notion.

3.3. Paired comparison ratios and significance levels of sub-criteria in terms of listening-comprehension criterion

According to the findings of the research, Poetry was seen to be first again with 20% when considering the significance levels of the literary texts in the acquisition of listening comprehension skills of teaching Turkish as FL. In this context, if the listening aspect of poetry is considered to be an important factor, it can be speculated that participants regard the poetry option to be an important factor in the development of listening comprehension skills.

Table 3.6: Significance Levels and Consistency Ratios of Sub-criteria in terms of
 Listening Comprehension Criterion

Listening Comprehension	Significance Level	Consistency
Poetry	0.20	
Stories	0.15	
Fables	0.10	
Fairy Tales	0.11	
Memoirs	0.08	
Conversa.-Interviews	0.08	4.85%
Commentary	0.07	
Theater plays	0.07	
Anecdotes	0.06	
Proverbs-Idioms	0.04	
Tongue twisters	0.04	

According to Table 3.6, after poetry, stories were seen to be important supplementary material at secondary level in the development of listening skills. The strong listening aspect of stories, like in poetry, influenced this outcome.

The literary texts with the third significance level in the development of listening skills are fairy tales with 11% ratio. Stressing the linguistic and expression aspects of fairy tales and their importance in language teaching, Yavuz (2009) explains the situation as such: *“The language in fairy tales is pure Turkish. Descriptions are quite a few in the narration. An active language dominates the whole of the fairy tale. Thus, they are not descriptive, but are highly action oriented. While adjectives are used less, verbs are used quite a lot. This is the main element that provides the mobility.”* In this regard, the purity of language in fairy tales makes it easier for students to understand them.

However, the literary texts that help to the development of listening skills are arranged as fables by 10%, memoirs, conversations-interviews by 8%, commentaries and theater plays by 7%, anecdotes by 6% and proverbs-idioms and tongue twisters by 4% respectively. The availability of audio poems, stories and fairy tales and students' ease of access to them might have affected the results to appear high.

3.4. Paired comparison ratios and significance levels of sub-criteria in terms of reading criterion

Table 3.7: Significance Levels and Consistency Ratios of Sub-criteria in terms of
 Reading Criterion

Reading	Significance Level	Consistency
Poetry	0.20	
Stories	0.23	
Novels	0.12	
Fables	0.08	
Fairy Tales	0.15	8.56%
Memoirs	0.07	
Essays	0.06	
Letters	0.05	
Anecdotes	0.04	

According to Figure 3.7, stories were identified to be the most important literary text with the ratio of 23% in teaching of reading skills of Turkish as FL. Poetry was seen to be the literary text with the secondary level of importance with 20% in the development of reading skills in teaching Turkish as FL. The high ratio of poetry may be associated with the poetry recitation ability (from memory or text) of the teachers participated in the research.

At the end of the research, the participants attracted attention to the fairy tales by 15% from literary texts in the development of reading skills of Turkish as FL. Fairy tales, which consist of simple sentences, have great importance especially in the development of students' reading skills at intermediate level.

According to the findings of the research, another important literary text that affects the development of reading skills of Turkish as FL is novel with the rate of 12%. In this context, novels, which will attract the interest of young people, are important especially at intermediate and advanced levels.

This ranking was followed by fables with 8%, memoirs with 7%, essays with 6%, and letters with 5% and anecdotes with 4% respectively. Literary texts, which allow teachers to save classes from monotony, have a special importance particularly in the development of reading skills.

3.5. Paired comparison ratios and significance levels of sub-criteria in terms of writing criterion

The result for the most effective literary text in the development of writing skills of Turkish as FL can be seen as stories with 19% in Table 4.6.2. Participants agreed upon fairy tales to be the second most effective literary text by 17% in the development of writing skills. Kibris (2008) states that fairy tales, as writing practice, may be asked to be

re-written by changing their narrative perspectives, characters, settings and time. In this context, fairy tales are seen to be used in the acquisition of writing skills.

Table 3.8. Significance Levels and Consistency Ratios of Sub-criteria in terms of Writing Criterion

Writing	Significance Level	Consistency
Poetry	0.14	
Stories	0.19	
Fairy Tales	0.17	
Memoirs	0.13	3.71%
Dairies	0.12	
Biographies	0.09	
Essays	0.08	
Letters	0.07	

According to the findings, other literary texts in teaching writing skills of Turkish as FL were ranked as poetry by 14%, memoirs by 13%, biographies by 9%, essays by 8% and letters by 7% respectively.

3.6. Paired comparison ratios and significance levels of sub-criteria in terms of teaching vocabulary criterion

Table 3.9: Significance Levels and Consistency Ratios of Sub-criteria in terms of Teaching Vocabulary Criterion

Teaching Vocabulary	Significance Level	Consistency
Poetry	0.09	3.44%
Stories	0.12	
Novels	0.11	
Fables	0.09	
Fairy Tales	0.10	
Memoirs	0.08	
Dairies	0.07	
Biographies	0.06	
Essays	0.06	
Theater plays	0.06	
Letters	0.05	
Anecdotes	0.04	
Proverbs-Idioms	0.04	
Tongue twisters	0.03	

In the research, stories were seen to rank the first in teaching vocabulary by 12% and novels ranked the second by 11% in the acquisition of writing skills. It is possible to

state that students learn terms except the words used in everyday speech from stories and novels.

The ranking was followed by fairy tales with 10%, poetry and fables with 9%, memoirs with 8%, dairies with 7%, essays, biographies and theater plays with 6%, letters with 5%, anecdotes, proverbs-idioms with 4% and tongue twisters with 3% respectively.

It is necessary to address the words with their different aspects and to evaluate them with all of their formats in their use in the texts when considering the role of literary texts in teaching vocabulary.

Words should have four aspects like;

- a. Dictionary meaning
- b. deeper meaning,
- c. Its meaning within culture,
- d. Its meaning in conversation

and literary texts have great importance in the comprehension of these aspects. This approach reveals the necessity to use literary texts to teach different meanings of the word in addition to its dictionary meaning while teaching vocabulary (Üstten, 2010). The instrumentality of literary texts is understood better in this context.

3.7. Paired comparison ratios and significance levels of sub-criteria in terms of grammar criterion

Table 3.10: Significance Levels and Consistency Ratios of Sub-criteria in terms of Grammar Criterion

Teaching Grammar	Significance Level	Consistency
Poetry	0.13	
Stories	0.17	
Novels	0.15	
Fables	0.11	
Fairy Tales	0.14	4.86%
Memoirs	0.09	
Dairies	0.08	
Essays	0.07	
Letters	0.06	

The significance levels of literary texts in teaching grammar ranked as stories by 17%, novels by 15%, fairy tales by 14%, poetry by 13%, fables by 11%, memoirs by 9%, dairies by 8%, essays by 7%, and letters by 6% respectively. Rules and forms of grammar can gain functionality by selecting suitable literary texts. The instrumentality of literary texts cannot be denied in the comprehension of language structures, checking whether

the subject was understood or not and reinforcing the previously-taught grammatical structures.

3.8. Paired comparison and significance levels of sub-criteria in terms of cultural transmission criterion

In the research, novels and stories, by the ratio of 12%, were identified to be the most important types as literary texts in cultural transmission of Turkish as FL. This was followed by fairy tales and fables with 10%. Poetry was determined to have significance level at the ratio of 9%, memoirs and conversation-interviews at 7%, dairies and theater plays at 6%, commentaries and essays at 5%, and letters, anecdotes and proverbs-idioms at 4% respectively.

Table 3.11: Significance Levels and Consistency Ratios of Sub-criteria in terms of Cultural Transmission Criterion

Cultural Transmission	Significance Level	Consistency
Poetry	0.09	
Stories	0.12	
Novels	0.12	
Fables	0.10	
Fairy Tales	0.10	
Memoirs	0.07	
Conversation-Interviews	0.07	
Dairies	0.06	4.87%
Commentaries	0.05	
Essays	0.05	
Theater Plays	0.06	
Letters	0.04	
Anecdotes	0.04	
Proverbs-Idioms	0.04	

Foreign language teaching is also teaching of culture. People express themselves with the words of the community to which they belong and the culture of that community. All of these require a cultural history. Therefore, teaching a language outside its own logic while disregarding the social structure and values of that language will make it difficult to learn that foreign language (Pehlivan, 2007:12). In this context, the language will be taught along with the culture of that language through the use of literary texts. Students will be able to look at the world with tolerance by comparing similarities and differences between their own culture and foreign culture.

3.9 The relationship between literary texts and language levels

Relationship between literary texts with language levels was attempted to be identified by multi-choice method. In this context, poetry, stories, novels, fables, fairy tales, memoirs, conversation-interviews, dairies, biographies, commentaries, essays, theater plays, letters, anecdotes, proverbs-idioms and tongue twisters were individually compared with language levels and which literary text is used the most at which level was determined.

Table 3.12: Relationship between Literary Texts and Language Levels

Literary Texts	Poetry	Novels	Stories	Fairy Tales	Fables	Convers.-Interviews	Memoirs	Dairies
Language Levels								
A1	2.9%	.9%	4.0%	7.8%	11.5%	3.0%	1.9%	6.1%
A2	9.8%	6.4%	18.8%	16.7%	13.3%	11.9%	15.2%	15.2%
B1	18.6%	12.8%	15.8%	14.7%	17.1%	14.9%	17.1%	14.1%
B2	13.7%	16.5%	16.8%	12.7%	15.2%	15.8%	17.1%	14.1%
C1	14.7%	26.6%	9.9%	14.7%	11.4%	14.9%	14.3%	13.1%
C2	17.6%	26.6%	11.9%	12.7%	13.3%	16.8%	13.3%	14.1%
All of them	21.6%	10.1%	22.8%	20.6%	19.0%	19.8%	19.0%	20.2%
None	1.0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	3.0%	1.9%	3.0%

Table 3.13: Relationship between Literary Texts and Language Levels

Literary Texts	Biography	Comment.	Essays	Theater Plays	Letters	Anecdote	Proverbs-Idioms	Tongue twisters
Language Levels								
A1	7.4%	7.4%	2.1%	3.8%	16.4%	5.3%	4.7%	16.4%
A2	15.8%	14.7%	7.4%	12.3%	17.3%	16.8%	12.3%	14.4%
B1	15.8%	13.7%	11.7%	16.0%	13.3%	14.2%	15.1%	13.3%
B2	10.5%	14.7%	19.1%	17.0%	12.2%	14.2%	13.2%	10.0%
C1	14.7%	11.6%	18.1%	17.9%	16.3%	14.2%	16.0%	4.4%
C2	16.8%	16.8%	25.5%	16.0%	18.4%	15.0%	15.1%	6.7%
All of them	16.8%	17.9%	14.9%	17.0%	3.1%	19.5%	22.6%	28.9%
None	2.1%	3.2%	1.1%	0%	0%	.9%	.9%	7.8%

The most commonly used literary texts at A1 level were listed as letters and tongue twisters by 16.4% and fables by 11.5% when examining the relationship between literary texts in Tables 4.10.1a and 4.10.1b and language levels. Letters are the most effective literary texts in which everyday language is being used when looking at word availability at basic level since they include the most commonly used structures in language. Electronic mails may also have been effective at this rate with the

advancement of technology. Tongue twisters' being at the same ratio with letters by 16.4% indicate that they are among the literary texts used at basic level since they include review features for sentence structure of that language and the comprehension of the properties in the acquisition of pronunciation skills. Fables' ranking at the third place by 11.5% suggest that their inclusion of everyday events, involvement with animals that students are familiar with, dynamism in narrations and closeness to representation make them most important factor in using them at basic level. Other literary texts at A1 level were ranked as fairy tales with 7.8%, biographies and commentaries with 7.4%, dairies with 6.1%, anecdotes with 5.3%, proverbs and idioms with 4.7%, theater plays with 3.8%, conversation-interview with 3%, poetry with 2.9%, essays with 2.1%, memoirs with 1.9% and novels with 0.9% respectively.

At A2 language level, the ranking occurred as stories with 18.8, letters with 17.3% and anecdotes with 16.8% respectively. Shortness of stories, simplicity of their narration, and their ability to solve the story line through words that students already know might have made them effective at this level. This ranking was followed by fairy tales with 16.7%, biographies with 15.8%, memoirs and dairies with 15.2%, commentaries with 14.7%, tongue twisters with 14.4%, fables with 13.3%, theater plays, proverbs and idioms with 12.3%, conversation-interviews with 11.9%, poetry with 9.8%, essays with 7.4% and novels with 6.4% respectively.

Literary text with the highest significance level at B1 level in Figures 4.10.1a and 4.10.1b is poetry with the ratio of 18.6%. Memoirs and fables with 17.1%, theater plays with 16% and stories and biographies with 15.8% are ranked respectively after poetry. In this context, liveliness of language in poetry, their rousing of pleasant feelings in people and wakening of pleasure of language in students make it the most commonly literary texts. The use of simple and fluent style in memoirs rather than fancy narration put them in the second place as an effective literary text when considering the vocabulary powers of students at B1 level. Other effective literary texts are ranked as proverbs-idioms with 15.1%, conversation-interviews with 14.9%, fairy tales with 14.7%, anecdotes with 14.2%, dairies with 14.1%, commentaries with 13.7%, letters and tongue twisters with 13.3%, novels with 12.8% and essays with 11.7% respectively.

The most effective literary text at B2 level is essay by the ratio of 19.1% and the freedom of choosing topic in essays and the ability to compose it by looking at previously written similar writings may be the reason why essays are seen as the most effective literary text at this level. Memoirs were seen to be effective at the ratio of 17.1%, theater plays by 17%, stories by 16.8%, novels by 16.5%, conversation-interviews by 15.8%, fables by 15.2%, commentaries by 14.7%, anecdotes by 14.2%, dairies by

14.1%, poetry by 13.7%, proverbs-idioms by 13.2%, fairy tales by 12.7%, letters by 12.2%, biographies by 10.5%, and tongue twisters by 10% at B2 level. In this context, while literary texts that are effective at basic level, which we call A1 and A2 levels, were seen to fall as a percentage at intermediate level, which we call B1 and B2 levels, literary texts used at intermediate level became different.

Effective literary texts at C1 level were seen to be novels by 26.6%, essays by 18.1% and theater plays by 17.9% in Tables 4.10.1a and 4.10.1b. Novels have a great impact on students because they arouse curiosity and attract readers within themselves in the context of the story line. Novels' acquisition of first place at C1 level may be because students' language level reached at a certain level. The ranking was followed by letters with 16.3%, proverbs and idioms with 16%, conversation-interviews with 14.9%, poetry, fairy tales and biographies with 14.7%, memoirs with 14.3%, anecdotes with 14.2%, dairies with 13.1%, commentaries with 11.6%, fables with 11.4%, stories with 9.9% and tongue twisters with 4.4% respectively.

Novels 'acquisition of the first place at C2 level with 26.6% as the most effective literary text can be explained by the necessity for students to know descriptions, secondary and tertiary meanings in the language. Essays had the secondary effectiveness with 25.5% and letters had the third with 18.4%. The ranking occurred as poetry with 17.6%, conversation-interviews, biographies and commentaries with 16.8%, theater plays with 16%, proverbs and idioms with 15.1%, anecdotes with 15%, dairies with 14%, fables and memoirs with 13.3%, fairy tales with 12.7%, stories with 11.9%, and tongue twisters with 6.7% respectively.

When considering all of the levels of language, tongue twisters took the first place with 28.9% in respond to the question "*which one of the questions are used in all levels?*" directed at the teachers who participated in the research. Tongue twisters were seen to be used especially in the development of pronunciation because they include poetic elements within themselves and they are short and quite appealing. This ranking was followed by stories with 22.8%, proverbs and idioms with 22.6%, poetry with 21.6%, fairy tales with 20.6%, dairies with 20.2%, conversation-interviews with 19.8%, anecdotes with 19.5%, memoirs and fables with 19%, commentaries with 17.9%, theater plays with 17%, biographies with 16.8%, essays with 14.9%, novels with 10.1% and letters with 3.1% respectively. The response of the participants to the question "*which literary text is not used in none of the language levels?*" to appear as tongue twisters with the ratio of 7.8% indicates that some of the teachers, who participated in the survey, never used tongue twisters in their classes. Tongue twisters were seen to be less when

examining the textbooks of teaching Turkish as FL. Teachers, who carry out textbook-oriented teaching, were assumed to affect this ratio.

4. Conclusions and suggestions

4.1. Conclusions

The significance levels of literary texts were determined in the context of their effect in the development of language skills in teaching Turkish as FL according to the results of the research. It was concluded that literary texts were mostly used effectively in speaking skills among other language skills in teaching Turkish as FL. This ranking was followed by listening comprehension, reading, writing, teaching vocabulary, grammar and cultural transmission respectively.

Stories were seen to take the first place among literary texts that prove to be effective in the acquisition of language skills. Shortness of stories, simplicity of their narration, and their ability to solve the story line through words that students already know might have made them effective as a literary text. Fairy tales occupied the second place. Plainness of story line in fairy tales and the simplicity of their language might have made those who teach Turkish as FL to prefer them. Poetry, novels and fables, memoirs, conversation-interviews, dairies, biographies, commentaries and theater plays, essays and letters, anecdotes, proverbs-idioms, and tongue twisters are ranked according to their significance levels.

Liveliness and effectiveness of poetry are important for the development of the target language in improving listening comprehension skills. The most effective literary texts, after poetry, are ranked as stories, fairy tales, fables, memoirs, conversation-interviews, commentaries, theater plays, anecdotes, proverbs-idioms and tongue twisters with regard to significance levels. In this context, if this ranking is taken into account in the preparation of textbooks and reading books, more accurate results may be obtained in the teaching of literary texts.

The reason why stories are the most effective literary text in the development of reading skills in teaching Turkish as FL may be explained their shortness of stories, simplicity of story line and not including too much details. International Turkish Olympiads, organized in recent years, can be said to be effective in the ranking of poetry as the second most effective literary text in reading skills after stories. This ranking is followed by fairy tales, novels, fables, memoirs, essays, letters and anecdotes respectively. Literary texts, which will be prepared particularly for the levels of teaching Turkish as FL, will make the tasks of teachers easier in teaching Turkish as FL.

The most effective literary texts for the development of writing skills are determined to be stories due to their shortness and simplicity of events. Next to stories, the most effective literary texts in teaching Turkish as FL are fairy tales. Re-writing the fairy after changing the plot, setting and time might have become effective in the development of writing skills. This ranking was followed by poetry, memoirs, dairies, biographies, essays and letters respectively. Here, the frequency of use of literary texts in textbooks or reading books of Turkish as FL may have influenced these results.

The most effective literary text in teaching vocabulary while teaching Turkish as FL was determined to be stories. Next to teaching vocabulary, the most influential literary text was identified to be novels which cover issues, lives and cultures that students feel curious about. In the following ranking, poetry, fables, memoirs, dairies, essays, biographies, theater plays, letters, anecdotes, proverbs-idioms and tongue twisters were evaluated as the confirmed literary texts. In this context, since teaching vocabulary has an important place in teaching language, this is much more possible through literary texts.

The language skill that teachers consider to be the most difficult in teaching foreign language courses is grammatical skills. In this context, determining stories to be the most influential literary text in teaching grammar and novels and fairy tales as the second most influential literary texts draws attention to the importance of literary texts in teaching Turkish as FL since they save the class from the monotony especially when teaching grammar topics. This ranking was followed by poetry, fables, memoirs, dairies, essays and letters respectively.

Since teaching language is also teaching culture, the instrumentality of literary texts is quite important in this regard. The most effective literary texts in cultural transmission when teaching Turkish as FL were identified to be novels and stories. This ranking was determined to be followed by fairy tales, fables, poetry, memoirs, conversation-interviews, dairies, theater plays, commentaries, essays, letters, anecdotes and proverbs-idioms respectively.

The first three most effective literary texts at A1 level in teaching Turkish as FL are listed as letters, tongue twisters and fables. This finding can be said to be appropriate when considering the characteristics of the above-mentioned literary texts.

Stories, letters and anecdotes remain in the first rank of literary texts that are effective at A2 level. Inclusion of stories and anecdotes at A2 level as distinct from A1 level indicates that students already know the language at a certain level. In this

context, attention should be paid for the arrangement of literary texts that will be prepared according to level.

The effective literary texts at B1, which is the start of intermediate level, in teaching Turkish as FL are listed as poetry, memoirs and fables. In this ranking, different types of literary genres are seen to be used in the development of students' language levels contrary to beginner level.

The most effective literary texts at B2 level are essays, memoirs and theater plays. This indicates that students have already started to use the language they learn at this level. They understand essays, write their memories and they show that they use these skills with theater which is effective in listening comprehension skill.

The most effective literary texts at C1 level were identified to be novels, essays and theater plays. Essays' occupation of second place, even though they were in the first place at intermediate level, indicates that students' language levels have developed.

The most effective literary texts at C2 level in teaching Turkish as FL are novels, essays and letters respectively. These findings indicate that students already use the literary texts that will force their language levels at C2 which we also regard as the advanced level.

In the ranking of influential literary texts in all language levels, while tongue twisters secured the first place, this ranking was followed by stories, proverbs-idioms, poetry, fairy tales, dairies, conversation-interviews, anecdotes, memoirs, fables, commentaries, theater plays, biographies, essays, novels and letters respectively.

It is necessary to emphasize how, how much, and why literary texts need to be used in teaching Turkish to foreigners in instructional programs and course materials that will be prepared and to make sure that the selected literary texts will be eligible for cultural transmission.

4.2. Suggestions

- Since literary texts are effective in the development of language skills while teaching Turkish as FL, the materials appropriate for language level should be developed in this regard.
- Stories should be given sufficient places both in textbooks and reading books since their occupation of certain places especially in all of the language skills is an indication that they are widely used in teaching Turkish as FL. In addition, short story books, which are important in the development of reading and comprehension skills, should be prepared according to language levels.

- Multi-sensed supplementary materials should be prepared in the context of literary texts while preparing supplementary course materials in teaching Turkish as FL.
- It is necessary to give adequate places for poems in course books since they are effective particularly in the development of listening skills.
- Materials for literary texts that are effective in improving writing skills should be developed. In this context, stories, fairy tales, poetry, memoirs, dairies, biographies, essays and letters, whose rankings were found as a result of the research, should be included in textbooks and reading books according to their significance levels.
- Among literary texts, tongue twisters that can correct the pronunciation of difficult words should be identified and be made ready for use in teaching of difficult sounds and vocabulary while teaching Turkish as FL.
- Learning foreign language is through word learning. In this context, the most effective ones, from literary texts, should be prepared for vocabulary teaching. At the end of research, these literary texts were identified as stories, novels, fairy tales, poetry, fables, memoirs, dairies, essays, biographies, theater plays, letters, anecdotes, proverbs-idioms and tongue twisters respectively. This ranking should be respected in the preparation of course books and other materials.
- Visual stories and fairy tales, which are suitable for students' language levels and can also be used in their free time, can be prepared.
- Literary texts that will assist the comprehension of the structure taught can be developed for teaching grammar. In this context, supplementary course materials can be prepared by taking the results of the research into account. Teaching grammar can be realized by including literary texts in the textbooks used.
- Literary texts that can be effective in cultural transmission should be given adequate places in textbooks, reading books and supplementary course materials. The results of the research reveal the importance of using literary texts especially in cultural transmission.
- The staged literary texts should be prepared in order to save classes from monotony.
- Theater texts, which are appropriate for language level, should be written for arousing interest and curiosity in students.
- Vocalized literary texts should be designed in the context of allowing students to gain immediate access.

- Cinema adaptations of literary texts, which will prove to be most effective in cultural transmission like novels, stories and fairy tales, should be used in classes.
- Students can be ensured to learn language faster with literary text that will be prepared in the context of foreign language teaching methods.
- Literary texts, appropriate for language levels, should be prepared by using foreign language teaching techniques.

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THE DETERMINATION OF IMPACT OF LITERARY TEXTS THROUGH ANALYTICAL HIERARCHICAL
PROCESS ON DEVELOPMENT OF FUNDAMENTAL LANGUAGE SKILLS IN TEACHING OF
TURKISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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